

A Quantitative Portrait of Diamond Open Access in the European Union

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Abstract. Diamond Open Access (DOA) – where neither authors nor readers bear direct costs – is attracting growing institutional attention as an alternative framework for equitable scholarly communication. Despite the recent efforts to formalise its defining criteria and develop a dedicated discovery infrastructure, a systematic comparative analysis of DOA at the European regional scale remains lacking. This paper addresses that gap by providing a quantitative analysis of DOA publishing across EU countries, leveraging the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) as a curated source of DOA journals and the OpenAIRE Graph – a large-scale open Scientific Knowledge Graph – for article metadata and citation data from 2000 to 2024. Our methodology distinguishes between an author-side perspective (i.e., papers produced by researchers affiliated with a given country) and a journal-side perspective (i.e., papers published in journals hosted by that country), enabling characterisation of each country as a research producer, a publishing hub, or both. Results reveal consistent growth in DOA journal counts, article output, and citation accumulation across Europe. Significant national variation emerges: Croatia and Slovenia lead in DOA share relative to overall output; Spain and Poland dominate in absolute volume; and France stands out for citation impact and international journal attractiveness. Germany presents a structural asymmetry – hosting internationally visible DOA journals while domestic researchers engage comparatively little with the model. Notably, the Social Sciences, Arts, and Humanities predominate across all countries. These findings advance the scientometric understanding of open scholarly communication and highlight how shared digital infrastructures – such as open Scientific Knowledge Graphs and journal registries – enable large-scale monitoring of emerging publishing models.

Keywords: Diamond Open Access · Scientometrics · Scholarly communication · Open Science · European Union.

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1 Introduction

The transition from "pay-to-read" to "pay-to-publish" has long been perceived as replacing one flawed model with another. Increasingly, however, it appears to have produced a system in which the drawbacks of both coexist. This growing tension has led the scholarly community to reconsider alternative approaches to Open Access, most notably Diamond Open Access (DOA). In scholarly publishing, the widespread adoption of Article Processing Charge (APC)-based models has, in many cases, undermined the original ambition of Open Access to provide immediate, free, and unrestricted access to scientific knowledge. Rather than eliminating financial barriers, these models have largely redistributed them: institutions continue to bear subscription costs, while researchers are increasingly required to secure funding to cover rising APCs [13, 15, 17].

Against this backdrop, DOA has gained increasing attention as a potentially more equitable alternative, promoting inclusive and community-driven scholarly communication [1, 8, 19, 25]. Unlike market-based models such as subscription or APC-driven publishing, DOA relies on non-commercial funding mechanisms, shifting the economic logic of scholarly publishing from revenue generation to institutional and community-based support [10]. In this model, neither readers nor authors bear direct costs; instead, publishing is supported by funding bodies, research institutions, academic associations, and learned societies. Beyond its economic features, DOA is also framed as a way to restore greater control over scholarly communication to the academic community itself.

At the same time, DOA cannot be defined solely by the absence of APCs [21]. Recent initiatives – particularly the CRAFT-OA¹ and DIAMAS² projects – have proposed a more comprehensive framework, identifying a set of criteria that must be jointly satisfied for a journal to be considered genuinely DOA [6]. These include governance structures, ownership models, non-profit orientation, and the use of open, community-driven infrastructures. To operationalise this framework, the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH)³ has been developed as a tool for identifying journals that meet these criteria.

Both within the scientific community at large and in the field of academic communication studies, DOA has attracted increasing attention in recent years. Existing research has examined its diffusion at both global and national levels; however, a gap remains at the regional scale, particularly in Europe. This analysis addresses this gap by analysing the diffusion, characteristics, and impact of DOA across European countries to identify and compare emerging national patterns.

At the European level, recent policy-oriented analyses highlight both the growing institutional support for non-profit Open Access publishing and the considerable diversity in governance models, funding mechanisms, and cross-country coordination, pointing to a fragmented and heterogeneous landscape [16]. In this context, countries with well-established national infrastructures for institutional,

¹ <https://www.craft-oa.eu>

² <https://diameterproject.eu>

³ <https://ddh.edch.eu>

non-profit Open Access publishing, such as Croatia, Finland, France, Spain, and Portugal, tend to host more mature, coordinated, and thriving communities of DOA journals.

While existing quantitative studies on DOA have focused primarily on journals and infrastructures (e.g., [26, 9]), less attention has been paid to authors' publishing behaviour within the DOA landscape. This analysis introduces an author-centred perspective to investigate how researchers engage with DOA as a dissemination channel. In this regard, the paper adopts two complementary analytical perspectives throughout the results section. The first is an *author-side* perspective that counts papers authored by researchers affiliated with a given country, regardless of the journal's editorial location. The second is a *journal-side* perspective, which counts papers published in journals based in a given country, regardless of the authors' affiliations. This distinction is analytically important, as a country may be an active producer of DOA research without necessarily hosting a large DOA publishing infrastructure, and vice versa. This distinction allows analysis of national DOA ecosystems not only in terms of publishing infrastructures but also of authors' publishing behaviour, international attractiveness, and the transnational circulation of scholarly communication.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents related work framing the uptake of the DOA publishing model, while Section 3 describes the construction of the dataset used for this analysis. Section 4 reports the results for the quantitative analysis of the DOA landscape in Europe. Finally, Section 5 concludes by discussing the main findings of the study, and provides an overview of the main current limitations and future developments.

2 Related Work

Recent research on Diamond Open Access (DOA) has expanded significantly after 2020, reflecting the growing attention this model has received within the scholarly communication landscape [25]. Early contributions in this field focused primarily on defining DOA and situating it within the broader spectrum of Open Access models (e.g., [12]).

As the field has matured, several main research directions have emerged. A first major strand consists of quantitative analyses aimed at mapping the extent and distribution of DOA journals and articles [7, 9]. However, these approaches are frequently complemented by qualitative investigations, often based on surveys or interviews, to explore dimensions such as organisational structures, governance, and long-term sustainability. This concern is further reinforced by recent DIAMAS reports, which highlight significant cross-country variation in the development of DOA ecosystems, as well as a general lack of structural funding and a strong dependence on institutional support and volunteer labour. These factors are seen as potential constraints on the model's continuity, quality, and scalability [24].

Several studies have examined the funding models of DOA, showing that journals typically rely on a combination of institutional support, public funding,

in-kind contributions, and volunteer labour rather than market-based revenue streams [9, 25, 26].

More recent studies have shifted towards empirical comparisons between DOA and APC-based systems [20]. Sustainability, in particular, is widely identified as a central concern for DOA [5] given its reliance on non-commercial funding sources and institutional support. At the same time, other studies argue that the absence of profit-driven mechanisms may enable significantly lower operational costs, thereby making the model potentially more sustainable in the long term [8]. While DOA cannot be reduced to the mere absence of APCs [21], economic factors have nevertheless played a crucial role in its emergence and consolidation.

Several studies have examined the development of DOA at the national level, including analyses focusing on countries such as Norway [11], Croatia [22], Germany [25], Switzerland [14], the Netherlands [18], Canada [26], and Italy [4], where research has attempted not only to quantify the number of DOA journals and articles, but also to assess their visibility and impact.

Beyond patterns of national uptake, quantitative studies have also explored the disciplinary profile of DOA, often highlighting its strong presence in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) [9, 7, 4, 26]. However, these patterns are not universal [23] and require contextual interpretation, suggesting the need to combine quantitative mapping with context-sensitive qualitative analysis [25].

Another line of research focuses on scholars' perceptions and attitudes toward DOA, examining levels of awareness, perceived advantages, and barriers to adoption [18, 23, 25]. Additionally, [26] specifically examines its infrastructural dimension, emphasising the role of shared, non-commercial publishing infrastructures and institutional support systems.

Together, these strands of research have been essential in the literature for identifying and delineating the key characteristics of DOA, highlighting its multifaceted nature across economic, organisational, disciplinary, and infrastructural dimensions. Building on this body of work, this paper aims to further advance knowledge on DOA through a more fine-grained quantitative analysis focused on Europe.

3 Data and methods

This analysis aims to investigate the presence and impact of Diamond Open Access (DOA) in Europe using a set of quantitative indicators for DOA journals and their published articles.

The identification of DOA journals requires criteria that go beyond the mere absence of APCs [21]. For this reason, we relied on the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH), which provides a curated dataset of journals selected according to a comprehensive set of DOA criteria⁴. The DDH is therefore used as the primary source for identifying European DOA journals in this study.

⁴ <https://ddh.edch.eu/docs/diamond-journals>

Starting from this set of DOA journals, we constructed a dedicated dataset containing all articles published in these journals, as indexed in the OpenAIRE Graph. The OpenAIRE Graph⁵ is a large-scale, openly available scholarly knowledge graph that aggregates and interlinks metadata from a wide range of sources, including institutional repositories, publishers, data archives, and research information systems. It provides comprehensive coverage of research outputs – such as articles, datasets, and software – along with rich contextual information on authors, affiliations, funding, and citations.

The version of the OpenAIRE Graph used for this analysis – loaded in Google BigQuery⁶ – refers to a snapshot produced in October 2025 (publication date December 2025). Accordingly, we limited our analysis to articles published from 2000 to 2024, as coverage for 2025 would be partial. By leveraging the OpenAIRE Graph, we enriched the dataset and captured multiple dimensions of scholarly communication, including article volume, citation links, and institutional participation.

To analyse the disciplinary dimension, we used the Directory of Open Access Scholarly Resources (ROAD)⁷ to assign topics to the journals in scope. ROAD was selected because it is derived from the ISSN registry and explicitly covers open access journals.

The analysis is organised across four levels. Firstly, the analysis focuses on the European overview, which establishes aggregate trends in journal growth, paper output, citation accumulation, and disciplinary distribution, and introduces the top 10 countries by DOA article volume that characterise the remainder of the analysis: Croatia, the Czech Republic, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, and the Netherlands. Then, the analysis follows these countries along three complementary dimensions: publication patterns, citation impact, and disciplinary profiles.

As introduced in Section 1, the analysis combines an *author-side* and a *journal-side* perspective to capture both researchers' publishing behaviour and the role of national DOA publishing infrastructures. In addition, the share of papers authored entirely by researchers from outside the journal's country is used as a proxy for the international attractiveness of a country's DOA journals. These three lenses, together, allow for a more nuanced characterisation of each country's role in the DOA landscape – whether as a *research producer*, a *publishing hub*, or both – and provide the interpretive framework used consistently across Section 4.

4 Results

The results are organised across the four levels of analysis introduced in Section 3. Section 4.1 provides the European overview across aggregate trends in

⁵ <https://graph.openaire.eu>

⁶ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/cloud-access>

⁷ <https://road.issn.org>

(a) Active DOA journals per year in Europe (b) Cumulative sum of the number of articles published in European DOA Journals

(c) Cumulative sum of citations according to the citing paper year

Fig. 1: European Overview

journal growth, paper output, citation accumulation, and disciplinary distribution. Then, Section 4.2 analyses publication patterns for the top 10 countries, while their citation impact and disciplinary profiles are addressed by Section 4.3 and Section 4.4 respectively.

4.1 European Overview for DOA

We observe a growing trend in the number of active⁸ DOA journals in Europe (Figure 1a). Starting from 642 journals in 2000, the number increased almost fivefold to 3,222 in 2023, indicating a strong expansion of DOA over time, although this trend may partly reflect journals transitioning to this model during the period considered. The slight decline observed in 2024 (-23 journals) may instead reflect either further model transitions or journal cessations.

A similar trend can be observed in the number of articles published in European DOA journals (Figure 1b). However, a larger increase in article output occurs in 2021, with almost 6,000 more articles than the previous year.

⁸ A journal is considered active in a given year if there is at least one article published in the journal for the given year.

Fig. 2: Percentage of full foreign DOA articles received by European Union countries.

Figure 1c shows the distribution of citations to DOA papers in Europe. Here too, a clear growing trend is visible: citations to papers published in DOA journals increased from approximately 14 million in 2020 to more than 23 million in 2024. Note that, for a given year, the figure shows the total number of citations received up to that year, i.e., $\sum_{2000}^{Y-1} citations(y) + citations(Y)$. DOA papers receive, on average, around 1 million new citations per year, with more than 2 million from 2020 to 2024, demonstrating their growing uptake within the scholarly community.

Figure 2 shows a perspective on the impact of DOA journals per country, measured as the percentage of papers whose authors are entirely affiliated with institutions outside the journal’s country. This metric serves as an indicator of international appeal: when all contributing authors are foreign, it suggests that the journal attracts submissions based on its scientific reputation and visibility, rather than national proximity or institutional familiarity. Across Europe, a substantial share (42%) of articles published in DOA journals are authored entirely by researchers affiliated with institutions outside the journal’s country. The distribution, however, is highly uneven across countries, ranging from 81.0% in Romania to 18.0% in Spain. DOA journals in the Netherlands, France, Germany and Romania are highly attractive for foreign researchers. Poland, despite having a high number of DOA journals, shows a relatively low share of foreign authors, similarly to Italy and Spain. A detailed discussion of this indicator for the top 10 countries is provided in Section 4.2.

Figure 3 shows the distribution of DOA journals in Europe by discipline over the years and reveals a clear dominance of *Social Sciences*, and *Humanities and the Arts* journals (in green and purple). It also exhibits the most pronounced growth trend over the observed period, which is in line with observations from related research [9, 7, 4, 26]. Other disciplines show a positive trajectory as well,

Fig. 3: Distribution of DOA Journals per Discipline in Europe.

		DOA		Overall	
Country code	Country	Articles Produced	Tot. Articles	% DOA	
CZ	Czech Republic	23,571	382,593	6.16%	
DE	Germany	53,281	3,416,021	1.56%	
ES	Spain	188,243	2,083,629	9.03%	
FR	France	113,341	2,570,650	4.41%	
HR	Croatia	36,595	178,969	20.45%	
IT	Italy	84,927	2,374,426	3.58%	
NL	The Netherlands	<i>19,704</i>	1,545,234	<i>1.28%</i>	
PL	Poland	139,747	1,216,435	11.49%	
PT	Portugal	33,379	498,195	6.70%	
SI	Slovenia	23,903	<i>129,401</i>	18.47%	

Table 1: Top 10 countries authoring more DOA articles in Europe. Bold: highest value; italics: lowest value.

though their growth remains comparatively modest. The country-level breakdown of these disciplinary patterns is examined in Section 4.4.

Finally, Tables 1 and 2 show different perspectives of the uptake of DOA publishing in Europe for the ten countries with the highest number of authored DOA articles. Table 1 shows the percentage of DOA articles with respect to the overall article production of the country. Table 2 shows the number of DOA journals until 2024, the average number of papers in the journals of the country (column *journal-side*), and the yearly average of numbers of DOA papers in the ranges 2000–2019 and 2020–2024 (column group *author-side*).

Tables 1 and 2 together identify the ten countries that form the basis of the country-level analysis in the remainder of this study. As the tables show, these countries differ substantially both in the absolute volume of DOA output and in the share of DOA publishing relative to their overall publication activity – two dimensions that do not necessarily correlate. A detailed discussion of these patterns, including the distinction between author-side and journal-side production, is provided in Section 4.2.

These findings suggest that the uptake of DOA publishing is uneven across countries and does not directly correlate with the overall article production. For

Country	Journal-side		Author-side			
	Overall		2000-2019		2020-2024	
	Journals	Articles x Journal	Articles	AVG	Articles	AVG
Czech Republic	118	<i>199.4</i>	15,559	777.95	7,973	1,594.6
Germany	212	250.0	33,431	1,671.55	19,572	3,914.4
Spain	653	286.8	122,128	6,106.4	65,142	13,028.4
France	510	221.7	79,239	3,961.95	33,838	6,767.6
Croatia	162	225.6	24,411	1,220.55	12,134	2,426.8
Italy	417	201.3	53,652	2,682.6	30,281	6,056.2
The Netherlands	<i>79</i>	248.3	<i>13,509</i>	<i>675.45</i>	6,116	1,223.2
Poland	620	221.8	90,057	4,502.85	47,466	9,493.2
Portugal	142	234.1	21,323	1,066.15	11,921	2,384.2
Slovenia	114	208.5	17,845	892.25	<i>5,921</i>	<i>1,184.2</i>

Table 2: DOA journals and articles across the top 10 European countries (2000–2024). The Journal-side columns account for articles published in DOA journals based in the country. The Author-side columns account for DOA articles authored by researchers affiliated with the country. Bold: highest value; italics: lowest value.

instance, although Germany produces nearly eighteen times as many articles as Croatia, its share of DOA publishing is roughly one-twelfth of Croatia’s. A further trend that emerges is the consistent growth of DOA publishing in 2020–2024: compared to 2000–2019, all the countries show an increase in the average number of DOA papers published per year, ranging from +32.7% (Slovenia) to +113% in Spain and +134% in Germany.

4.2 Patterns of article production for the top 10 DOA publishing countries

This section analyses the papers published in DOA journals according to the two perspectives introduced in Section 3: the author-side perspective – papers produced by researchers affiliated with a given country – and the journal-side perspective – papers published in journals located in that country.

Figure 4a, Figure 4b, and Figure 4c are read in parallel throughout this section, as their joint interpretation is necessary to characterise each country’s role in the DOA ecosystem. Poland stands out with the highest number of DOA journals, exhibiting a decisive increase from 2007 onwards (see Figure 4a) – a trend likely reflecting targeted national policies to support and develop the DOA publishing infrastructure [16]. Spain and France held the first and second position until 2012, when they were surpassed by Poland, and have since split, with Spain showing a greater increase – in line with the trends reported for Europe overall. Notably, Spain and France both rank high in journal count, and, even if their share of DOA articles is not among the highest group, they produce the highest number of DOA papers in absolute numbers (see Figure 4b). The two countries, however, differ in submission pattern: France attracts a higher

(a) Active DOA Journals per country per year (b) Cumulative sum of articles per author's country

(c) Cumulative sum of Articles per publisher's country

Fig. 4: Diamond Open Access views per top 10 countries

share of foreign researchers, while Spain primarily serves a domestic audience (see Figure 2). Croatia is in fifth position in the number of DOA journals (see Figure 4a), with its journals attracting a balanced share of domestic and foreign authors (see Figure 2). Instead, Croatia leads in the share of authored papers published in DOA journals (20,45%, see Table 1). This divergence suggests that the production of DOA papers is not strongly tied to the availability of domestic DOA journals. Authors publishing in DOA venues do not necessarily rely on journals from their own country, suggesting a genuinely transnational dimension of DOA.

The same perspective from a different angle is shown in Figures 4b and 4c. The first shows the number of papers per country published in DOA journals (author-side perspective), while the second shows the number of papers published in DOA journals by the country of the journal (journal-side perspective). It can be observed that Spain ranks first among the top 10 countries in terms of the number of papers published in DOA journals and second in the number of articles appearing in Spanish DOA journals. Poland has seen a decisive increase in both categories over the last 10 years. France ranks third in article production in DOA journals, but first in DOA publishing. Germany presents a distinctive configuration: despite having one of the lowest shares of DOA publishing rela-

tive to its overall output (1.56%, see Table 1), it ranks fifth in absolute terms for both author-side and journal-side production. German journals attract a comparatively high share of entirely foreign-authored submissions (Figure 2). This pattern suggests that German DOA journals enjoy considerable international visibility, while domestic authors engage relatively little with DOA as a dissemination channel – a divergence that is further reflected in the citation analysis presented in Section 4.3.

The other countries show increases in both dimensions, but not to an outstanding degree. This dual perspective can help understand the nature of a country’s DOA activity: whether it is author-driven, infrastructure-driven, or both. France, for example, is third in the number of authored articles, but first in the number of published papers. This suggests France as a country with a strong, internationally visible DOA infrastructure that attracts foreign authors – consistent with the high share of entirely foreign-authored submissions shown in Figure 2. For Poland, instead, which is growing in both dimensions, we can think of a national push for DOA resulting in more papers and more journals.

4.3 Impact of DOA for the top 10 European countries

This section examines citation impact for the top 10 countries, focusing on the citations received by DOA papers. Three complementary perspectives are considered: the total number of citations received by papers published in each country’s DOA journals (Figure 5a); the citations received by DOA papers authored by at least one researcher affiliated with each country, broken down by publication date (Figure 5b) and by citation year (Figure 5c). The latter two figures offer complementary views on citation dynamics. Figure 5b shows citations according to the publication year of the cited paper, and is therefore subject to a recency bias: more recently published papers have less time to accumulate citations, making older papers appear disproportionately more cited. Figure 5c, by contrast, organises citations by the year in which they were made, offering a cleaner picture of how interest in DOA literature has evolved. The steady increase in citations observed in this latter figure over recent years points to growing recognition of DOA venues within the broader scholarly community, suggesting that DOA journals are progressively gaining in reputation and influence.

Taken together, these three perspectives confirm and extend the structural profiles identified in Section 4.2. Figure 5a identifies France and Germany as leaders in total citations received by papers published in their national DOA journals. As anticipated by the production analysis, however, Germany’s prominence at the journal level does not extend to the author level: its citation counts in Figures 5b and 5c are considerably lower, confirming that German DOA journals attract internationally visible submissions. In contrast, German researchers themselves publish comparatively little in DOA venues. France, by contrast, ranks highly across all three perspectives, indicating both a well-regarded national journal landscape and an active domestic DOA authorship – consistent with its role as a publishing hub that also produces a substantial share of the

Fig. 5: Citations received by DOA articles with at least one author’s affiliation in a top 10 country.

authored output. More broadly, the divergence between journal-level and author-level citation patterns observed across the top 10 countries suggests that citation impact in the DOA landscape is shaped not only by the volume of national publishing output but also by the international standing of domestic journals and the degree to which national research communities engage with DOA as a primary dissemination channel.

4.4 Dominant subjects for DOA publishing in the top 10 European countries

This section examines the distribution of topics covered by articles published in DOA journals across the European countries considered. Figure 6a and Figure 6b present the share of disciplines based on the Fields of Science (FoS) topic hierarchy from ROAD, split into two complementary perspectives: Figure 6a shows the disciplinary breakdown of articles with respect to the country of affiliation of the authors, while Figure 6b shows the disciplinary breakdown with respect to the country of the journal in which the article was published.

Nevertheless, taken together they offer a useful lens: when a country shows a low share of a given discipline from both the author and the journal perspective, this consistently points to that discipline being of limited interest or visibility

Fig. 6: Share of Discipline in the top 10 European Countries

within that country’s DOA ecosystem (for example, France on *engineering and technology*). Conversely, alignment between high author-side and high journal-side shares in a given discipline suggests that the topic represents a genuine area of national strength in DOA publishing or that the topic is highly considered in the country (e.g., like *natural sciences* in Germany). Across both perspectives, Social Sciences and Humanities and the Arts emerge as the dominant disciplines, reflecting the well-established affinity between these fields and DOA publishing models. Croatia is a notable exception, displaying a comparatively higher share of Engineering and Technology; however, this observation should be interpreted with caution, given that Croatia’s absolute volume of DOA papers is lower than that of the other mentioned countries, making its disciplinary distribution more sensitive to the composition of a relatively small set of journals.

5 Discussion

This paper examined national patterns in journal availability, author output, disciplinary coverage, and citation dynamics. The analysis shows consistent and widespread growth of DOA across Europe, evident across all main indicators, including the number of journals, published articles, citation impact, and the international attractiveness of DOA venues. This general upward trend, more evident in the number of articles and journals than in citations, suggests that the model is consolidating within the European scholarly communication landscape.

Important differences emerge at the national level. France stands out across several indicators, particularly in terms of citation impact and international visibility. Spain and Poland lead all countries in the number of DOA journals, while Spain ranks first in the absolute volume of DOA articles produced by domestic authors. Both countries display growth along both the author- and journal-side dimensions, suggesting a broad, structurally embedded commitment to the DOA model – though the mechanisms underlying this commitment may differ across the two national contexts.

However, when considering citation patterns and their origins, a more nuanced picture emerges: France ranks highly across all citation indicators considered, including both journal-level and author-level citation counts. This suggests

a high degree of international integration, consistent with its role as a publishing hub attracting foreign authors. For Spain, the comparatively lower share of entirely foreign-authored submissions in domestic journals suggests that its DOA publishing activity primarily serves a domestic author base. This pattern may also be consistent with the stronger role of national-language publishing and locally oriented research communities, particularly in countries where DOA activity is more strongly associated with the Social Sciences and Humanities.

Germany presents a distinctive configuration: it hosts a substantial number of DOA journals that attract a comparatively high share of entirely foreign-authored submissions – as shown in Figure 2 – and ranks among the leaders in journal-level citation counts. However, the share of DOA publishing relative to Germany’s overall output remains among the lowest in the top 10 (1.56%), and author-level citation counts are considerably lower than journal-level figures. This divergence points to a structural asymmetry: German DOA journals function as internationally visible venues, while German researchers themselves engage relatively little with DOA as their primary dissemination channel. These differences suggest that the adoption and development of DOA vary significantly across national contexts.

As for authors, the analysis reveals that authors’ behaviour in the European DOA landscape is characterised by a growing yet uneven adoption of DOA for scientific dissemination. As suggested by the comparison between author-side and journal-side production, authors do not necessarily publish in DOA journals based in their own country, indicating that journal selection is often driven more by visibility, reputation, and infrastructure quality than by national proximity. This transnational orientation is particularly visible in the Croatian case. Although Croatia ranks only fifth in the absolute number of DOA journals (Table 2), it exhibits the highest share of national output published in DOA venues (Table 1), suggesting a significant author-side engagement with the DOA model despite a comparatively smaller domestic DOA journal base.

At the same time, important differences emerge in the international attractiveness of national DOA systems. Countries such as the Netherlands, France, Romania and Germany attract a particularly high share of entirely foreign-authored submissions, indicating that their journals function as internationally visible publishing hubs. By contrast, Spain, Italy, and Poland appear more domestically oriented, with DOA publishing activity relying more strongly on national research communities. These differences suggest that DOA journals vary considerably in their degree of international integration and visibility. Germany again represents a particularly interesting case. German DOA journals attract a comparatively high number of foreign submissions and rank among the leading countries in journal-level citation impact. However, German authors themselves publish relatively little in DOA venues compared to the country’s overall publication output, and author-side citation counts remain considerably lower than journal-side figures. This asymmetry suggests a divergence between the international visibility of the national DOA publishing infrastructure and the level of domestic engagement with DOA as a dissemination model.

The present study is limited to quantitative indicators and does not directly assess the policy frameworks, funding conditions, or organisational structures that underlie the observed national patterns. The differences identified – in publication volume, journal attractiveness, and disciplinary orientation – are likely shaped by a combination of factors, including the availability of coordinated national funding mechanisms, the presence of established community-driven publishing infrastructures, and the broader academic culture of each country. Disentangling strategic policy choices from structural constraints – such as limited access to APC-based publishing funding – would require complementary qualitative investigation and represents a key direction for future research.

Social Sciences and Humanities and the Arts emerge as the dominant disciplines across most countries, while notable exceptions – such as Croatia’s relatively higher share of Engineering and Technology – point to nationally distinctive publishing cultures.

Moreover, this work is based on the Discovery Diamond Hub snapshot available at the time of writing. Despite its broad coverage, unbiased inclusivity, and continuous updates, the DDH does not yet include all DOA journals in Europe, which means the rankings reported here should be considered provisional and subject to change as coverage improves. Nevertheless, these data offer an initial basis for assessing the development of the DOA publishing model in Europe. As a complementary source of investigation, we plan to develop an AI-driven strategy to automatically detect DOA journals from scholarly data in the future.

Overall, the observed trends indicate that the DOA model is not only expanding but also consolidating its role within European scholarly communication. Consistent with the patterns discussed above, its development appears to be more pronounced in countries with favourable national conditions, including sustained support for non-commercial publishing, the availability of shared infrastructures, and a broader academic culture that values community-driven approaches to knowledge dissemination.

6 Data Availability

The dataset and queries used to perform the analysis in this article are available in Zenodo [3, 2].

7 Acknowledgment

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